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Does personality matter in system sustainability governance model?

Abstract. The article discusses the methodological issues of studying personality traits within the framework of the transformation governance model towards sustainable development. The integral approach proposed in the paper to study personality factors differs somewhat from existing research in the field of psychology, sociology, culture and other fields in several respects. It is based on the synthesis of the systemic economic paradigm and the paradigm of sustainable development, taking into account the influence of personality qualities through all possible channels. In this regard, a conceptual model was built to study the systemic interactions between sectors within the socio-economic system (SES) from the point of view of the influence of personality traits of individuals (or groups) as representatives of one or another sector. Some examples of such impact are given in relation to scientific and technological strategy in Russia. Sector's interactions and feedback mechanisms, as they contribute to the components of SES sustainability, are modeled in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Awareness the impact of personality traits on systemic connections and sustainability of SES in terms of global SDGs and internal balance in sector's interaction contributes to a deeper understanding of both sustainability governance mechanisms and the role of personality traits in the context of global transformations.

Keywords: sustainable development goals (SDGs), systemic economic paradigm, personality traits.

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Имеет ли значение личность в модели управления устойчивостью системы?

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются методологические вопросы изучения личностных качеств в рамках модели трансформационного управления в направлении устойчивого развития. Предложенный в статье интегральный подход к изучению личностных факторов отличается от существующих в психологии, социологии, культуре и других областях в нескольких отношениях. Он основан на синтезе системной экономической парадигмы и парадигмы устойчивого развития, учитывающей влияние личностных качеств по всем возможным

каналам. В связи с этим была построена концептуальная модель для изучения системных взаимодействий между секторами внутри социально-экономической системы (СЭС) с точки зрения влияния личностных черт отдельных лиц (или групп) как представителей того или иного сектора. Приведены некоторые примеры такого воздействия применительно к научно-технологической стратегии в России. Взаимодействия сектора и механизмы обратной связи, поскольку они вносят вклад в компоненты устойчивости СЭС, моделируются в соответствии с целями устойчивого развития (ЦУР). Осведомленность о влиянии личностных качеств на системные связи и устойчивость СЭС с точки зрения глобальных ЦУР и внутреннего баланса во взаимодействии сектора способствует более глубокому пониманию как механизмов управления устойчивостью, так и роли личностных качеств в контексте глобальных преобразований.

Ключевые слова: цели устойчивого развития (ЦУР), системная экономическая парадигма, личностные качества.

Introduction

The topic. The modern transformational crisis has affected all aspects of the economy and social life [17]. All layers of human society are forced to react in one way or another to cardinal changes in technologies, structures, motivations, approaches to goals and their activities:

- enterprises and organizations (interactive intelligent models of activity, virtual enterprises);
- individuals and social groups (teleworking, mobility, communication);
- government (changes in the apparatus, strategies, and programs);
- business (knowledge-based projects, investments, sources of income) [8; 14].

The essence of the pattern of such transformations lies in the fact that the global model is fundamentally changing based on the idea of sustainable development in order to avoid possible threats associated with the complication of technologies and activities with the growth of aggression in relations – both to nature and within the human community.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development prescribes transforming the relationship between people and their environment for social well-being and environmental preservation through good governance, public policy, knowledge and technology [19].

Agile governance problems increase in a non-stationary economy for the loss of its self-adaptation. This ability is essential for survival and underpins our interaction with the world around us. In particular, it is necessary to correctly react to changes and make adequate decisions. The trajectory of the society development largely depends on how a person behaves, especially if he is leader [13]. Personal traits influence the behavior: skill, desire, ability, psychology, mentality and other characteristics. Many global challenges relate to the sphere of human competencies, abilities and preferences; certain qualities are necessary to be investigated to make the strategies and decision-making to be corresponded to the contemporary trends of stability and integrity of the socio-economic system (SES).

The Russian strategic planning and governance is not adapted to the new factors of the transformational transition. The disunity of organizations of all branches of government and economic units signals a mismatch of interests and opinions about the goals and methods of actions in transformational period. This permeates the entire structure of the economy and manifests itself in the inconsistency of the content of the strategies, projects and programs. New trends pose new challenges and require coordinated strategic decisions for creation human-environment systems as self-developing system in dynamic.

Digitalization, Industry 4.0, green technologies strongly influence a person as an employee, manager, consumer, member of society. The changes make special demands on a person in all his roles. At the same time, their depth and degree of penetration into the SES tissue largely depend on the perception and actions of the subject of transformation – an individual or collective user, a transformer, a generator of new knowledge and technologies, as well as decision makers [4].

These arguments determine the relevance of the study of personal traits and associated influences. *Russian and foreign research.* The theory and methodological apparatus of behavioral economics is deeply developed [5]. But the links with the goals of the modern concept of sustainable development as applied to the innovative development model require more precise clarification, as in [21] point out, so they correlate behavior with the psychological characteristics of the personality in an era of change.

Personality problems in new models, in a green economy, are attracting more and more attention; their relevance for sustainability is undeniable [3]. According to the general opinion, the turn of the economy towards man and nature is an imperative and tendency of civilizational development [9]. However, studies of personality traits are not presented exhaustively in publications in relation to the governance for sustainable development in connection with the systemic laws of society. A wide range of researchers is studying environmental and social responsibility in governance (ESG) in the context of the sustainable development agenda [10], as well as psychological personality traits in the changing world, and, first of all, in relation to the person himself, but not to the economic system [1; 7; 16]. In addition there are practically no papers devoted to the study of personality traits inherent in actors as representatives of different sectors, and their influence on the consistency and harmonization of the interactions of the SES components.

Thus, systemic studies of the changing model of society and the person in it are quite relevant in the period of global changes. Such work should be interdisciplinary and should investigate the systemic patterns of sustainable development of the transforming SES on a base of the system theory.

In this regard, this paper discusses the methodological issues of the study of personal factors of stability, from the point of view, first, understanding the sustainability of the system in the four above-mentioned aspects; secondly, the inclusion of an individual or a group of persons as an economic entity in the interaction of various sectors of the SES and self-identification of the subject as part of a complex system in the context of a swap with mutually complementary flows of abilities between the sectors of the SES. Some progress in the synthesis of these two views is an element of the scientific novelty of this work. This is an ecosystem approach to the methodology of research and modeling of personality factors as a subject and object of SES, i.e. as a participant, executor and "consumer" of the adopted decisions, on which the trajectory of the SES depends. Understanding a SES as an ecosystem is a syncretic view of the world as a world of systems. Such a view determines the corresponding imperatives of the transformation of the personality in the strategy of sustainable development; they are also the subject of this study.

The following describes a synthetic approach to building a conceptual model for studying personality influences, and then discusses its possible applications.

Materials and methods

Let's understand SES, according to the system economic paradigm [12], as the integral unity of four key sectors: economy, society, state, business. They are systems of different types, respectively: an object system, an environment system, a process system and a project system in SES. They are interacting through the swap of resources (abilities) of various kinds. This interacting is influenced by many conditions and factors, including persons (the so-called "Subjects" – individuals or groups representing any sector). All these influences, including personal qualities, determine the degree of sustainability of the SES. The adaptability and reactivity of the system greatly affects SES homeostasis in a changing environment.

The concept of sustainable development, proclaimed by the UN, includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [19]; they can be classified as four dimensions of the vector of the SES sustainable development strategy: (1) global environmental commons; (2) human well-being; (3) sustainable and just economies; (4) science and technologies. The SDGs form the basis for the development of SES strategies at different levels of the hierarchy as a guide for decision-makers.

Prerequisite is that the degree of freedom of the person's activity depends on the formal and informal institutional and economic frameworks in the system and the environment, as well as on personality traits and the consequences of the actions in all sectors.

This study examines sustainability from the point of view of the synthesis of the systemic paradigm of economics and the paradigm of sustainable development in the global SDG agenda. The synthesis of two such paradigms involves considering SES sustainability from different angles, characterizing understanding of sustainability in the context of the SDGs in terms of the spatial-temporal characteristics of resource flows between SES sectors that contribute to sustainability. In addition this approach follows the idea of polycentric systems [4] as shown below, and places it in conceptual models designed to study the factors influencing the sustainability of SES, based on self-organization in different situations with external and internal influences.

Results

According to the integral approach, sustainability is considered in four aspects. To do this, we put the hypostasis of SES sustainability [19] in line with the structure of interacting SES sectors, according to [12]:

- 1) the SES capability for sustainability as a complex of immanent properties, for example, the ability to adapt – an internal environment system that is not limited either in time or in space;
- 2) SDGs strategies, policy and governance – a process system, limited in time, not limited in space;
- 3) the design solutions for specific areas, aimed as a rule at ESG – a project system limited in time and in space;
- 4) the objective state of the system and its activity (for example, ways of using energy resources, the level of innovation activity) – an object system, limited in space, not limited in time.

In this view, the hypostasis of SES stability can be depicted as stability control subsystems in the form of a structural-functional model of systems linkages and interactions of different types (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Subsystems in the concept of SES sustainability

Source: developed by the authors.

Such a view helps to investigate SES in the interconnection of the four hypostases of stability and to clarify the possible mechanisms of the influence of personality traits within the framework of a multi-agent model of interactions, taking into account the spatio-temporal characteristics of resources (or capabilities) that are exchanged between components (subsystems) through direct channels and feedback.

The structural and functional model (fig. 2) is the result of the interpretation of an integral approach that combines three points: (1) a four-dimensional vision of subsystems in SES stability concept (fig. 1); (2) inclusion of the global SDGs paradigm into a polycentric governance model; (3) presentation SES as a tetrad within the framework of Kleiner's system economic paradigm.

1. Environment capacity – the ability of SES to adapt and to be sustainable – includes organizational culture, intellectual, psychological and ideological abilities; they are largely related to the personality traits of individuals and how they are incorporated into the SES. Ways for improvement: creating suitable environments (social, moral, cultural, intellectual, institutional, etc. and nature).

2. National or regional SDGs strategies, policies and governance include strategic decisions and regulatory impacts; they depend on the preferences, mentality and other traits of the governance actors and decision-makers at the high level of economy. Ways for improvement: improving the pattern of planning and governance, e.g. due to consensus of stakeholders in goal-setting and reflection.

3. Projects for sustainable development in some area are formed as a result of the transfer national SDGs strategies and relevant governance instruments to the entrepreneurial level. Ways for improvement: (1) entrepreneur ESG responsibility; (2) tuning institutional, organizational and economic governance in the task of correlating SDGs, ESG business strategy, and results to increase motivation for sustainable development.

4. The state of economic entities and their ESG activity are determined by the quality of both entrepreneurial projects and the performance ESG; this point depend to a large extent on the ways of using resources, management, motives and competencies of the persons making and executing decisions.

Fig. 2. Structural and functional model of SES stability governance

Note: ☺ – a sign of human influence on the direct and feedback.
 Source: developed by the authors based on [12; 19].

The impact of personality traits is modeled, respectively, in the form of spheres of influence of actors, whose behavior affects (1) the activity of the SES sectors and the flows of resources (abilities) between them, (2) the components of the sustainability of the SES, and (3) the results of the implementation of the SDG strategy based on the mechanisms of direct and feedback.

The novelty includes: (1) setting the task of identifying the relationship between personality traits and steps of the SES towards sustainable development in accordance with the SDGs; (2) a new format for studying such relationships within the framework of a holistic concept of sustainable development and system economic theory. The synthesis of these two paradigms is based on the coverage of all subsystems of the SES and the person in them performing different roles – since he is the subject of the intellectual, institutional and mental spheres, as well as planning, management, decision-making, implementation of the SDGs and ESG strategies, reflective analyzing of both results

and oneself in the SES, and it is also the object of all changes. In this case, subjects (individuals or groups) are considered as stakeholders in a particular subsystem in the process of interaction of several subsystems (sectors) of the SES. The essential point of the approach is that one and the same entity can be considered as a stakeholder acting on the part of several sectors.

Discussion

The requirement for the SES sustainability in reference to it as an ecosystem, presupposes harmony of interactions between human, nature and other parts of an integral system. Then the only way out for a person as a SES participant who shares the SDGs and ESG is to be systemic, that is, to identify oneself as part of a holistic SES. His consistency is expressed in such traits of mentality, values and interests that can help him see the world of systems in the world around him and see himself in it. Such systemic thinking and systemic vision is expressed in his behavior, which is influenced by both personality traits, different environments, and the consequences of the activities of various parties. This consideration puts forward a number of requirements both for the creation of the environment and for the ways for personality development based on harmony, in contrast to postmodernism. The position “every man for himself” can be considered non-systemic, it cannot be constructive in the long term, when the world faces a fateful choice for the future, and an increasing number of participants are inclined to adhere to the SDGs. Such relationships can be explored using multi-agent models like the one above.

The presented models need empirical testing. Informational support of these models can help to test hypotheses about the directions and degree of influence of the factors under study. The research problem is that indicators of personal aspirations, as well as decision-making criteria, are difficult to quantify; there is not even an approximate data. In this case, personality traits can be observed as traces, i.e. as the conformity of actions and decisions taken in certain conditions of various environments, adherence to the SDGs, as well as the consequences of such decisions. For example, in the absence of an institution of responsibility in Russia, no framework, with the exception of personal qualities, limits the actions of most senior officials or top managers. In this regard, there is a desire to expand access to administrative and financial resources, as well as to retain power, chair and methods of generating rental income.

In government documents, one can find recognition of the relevance of fundamental research in the field of sustainable development of the economy in its close relationship with nature, man and the techno-sphere. The program for the development of Russian science sets the goal: “obtaining new knowledge about the basic laws of the structure, functioning and development of man, society, nature, which are necessary for sustainable scientific, technological, socio-economic and cultural development of the country...” [11]. “Quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the parameters of sustainable development of the Russian Federation” are formulated as priority areas in accordance with the first paragraph of the program of economic sciences [11, p. 91]. However, in reality, the scientific and technical strategy of the Russian Federation, as well as the corresponding national projects, programs and state policy are focused, in fact, on “scientometric” and rating indicators, which do not and cannot lead to the stability of the SES in any of its dimensions, despite repeated critical comments of experts and scientists [2; 20]. Thus, the practice of strategic planning demonstrates noticeable differences between the formally proclaimed goals of sustainable development in the CES strategies and the true intentions of economic agents. It was not possible to reach consensus either on this or on other issues on the sustainable development agenda at any level of the hierarchy.

Conclusion

It becomes obvious from the study of the model and practice that each of the players representing any SES sector is inclined not to worsen his position under given the rules of the game. So it is necessary to change the “rules of the game” and the “playing of the game” in the direction of compliance with the SDGs, taking into account the peculiarities of the country, systemic linkages, and interactions of sectors in which the social sector (environment subsystem) plays a leading

role, since society forms an informal institutional environment, as well as an intellectual and moral environment.

The state, represented by senior managers, is responsible for setting the institutional environment in line with the SDGs in the country's strategy, policy and governance in the national interest. Due to the difference in interests, a consensus of opinions of the state, people, specialists and entrepreneurs is needed regarding the vector of movement of the SES and its parts in accordance with the global transformation [22].

Various methods and models can be used to study possible ways of reconciling opinions, relations, in general, attitudes for cases of rational or irrational behavior of an agent in various conditions of the environment in which he acts [15]. In contrast to them, this model is of a framework nature for studying the relations and conditions of sustainable development from the standpoint of system economic theory and a systemic understanding of the concept of sustainability.

To conclude, sustainable development requires socio-technical images of the transforming system to humanize technological progress [6]. This is possible through a systematic synthesis of several paradigms, as follows from the model presented above. Conclusions from the presented approach imply the imperatives of human transformation in a wide range of characteristics. More and more researchers are coming to this conclusion [4; 18]. We include ecosystem thinking in a number of major impacts. A systematic understanding of personality factors and their influence on the state and dynamics of SES can contribute to self-organization and self-development.

Further study of the topic is promising in terms of interdisciplinary research. It will be useful to conduct a quantitative assessment of the factor dependences of the sustainability indicators of SES with personality traits in various technological and economic dynamics.

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